

Extraction, Spectrophotometric and Fluorimetric Determination of Submicrogram Quantities of Aluminium with *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid and Morin

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Manuscript received 5 September 1983, accepted 26 May 1984

The spectrophotometric and fluorimetric method for the determination of aluminium(III) with *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) and morin have been developed. The determination is based on the extraction of aluminium-PBHA complex into chloroform in ammonium carbonate medium and then forming its complex with morin. The greenish yellow coloured aluminium-PBHA-morin complex has a maximum absorbance at 430 nm with a molar absorptivity $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and gives the fluorescence.

SEVERAL spectrophotometric and fluorimetric methods are described for the determination of aluminium. Generally, the methods are based on measuring the colour intensity formed by aluminium with the various lake forming reagents, such as alizarin-S, alizarin-S with calcium, aluminon, eriochrome cyanin-R *etc.*¹. But these methods are not useful as the reactions are slow, and composition, consistency and reproducibility of colours are uncertain. Moreover, the methods are non-selective due to more interferences of diverse ions¹. Pontachrome blue black R², hematoxylin³ and morin³ were also used for fluorimetric determination of aluminium. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) along with 8-quinolinol in ammonium carbonate medium in presence of thioglycollic acid, hexametaphosphate, hydrogen peroxide and potassium cyanide as masking agents, was used for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of aluminium⁴.

In the present investigation a method has been developed for the rapid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of aluminium(III) in ammonium carbonate medium with PBHA, and then forming an adduct type complex with morin. The aluminium-PBHA-morin complex is greenish yellow in colour and also gives fluorescence. Hence the aluminium is determined, in microgram quantities, spectrophotometrically and fluorimetrically.

Experimental

The spectrophotometric and fluorimetric measurements were made on Varian Superscan-3 spectrophotometer and Systronic 151 photofluorimeter, respectively.

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR and G.R. grades of B.D.H. or E. Merck respectively, unless otherwise specified. Synthesis of PBHA (m.p. 121°)

has been described elsewhere⁵. The purity of freshly prepared reagent (PBHA) was checked by tlc, ir and uv spectra. A 0.5% (w/v) reagent solution was prepared in ethanol. Dilutions were made with ethanol whenever it was required. Morin 0.1% (w/v) solution was prepared in ethanol and dilutions were made whenever required. 20% (w/v) aqueous ammonium carbonate solution was used. Requisite amount of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in distilled water. The final concentration of aluminium (III) solution was determined volumetrically⁶.

An aliquot of standard aluminium solution (0.3 ppm) was made upto 5 ml with distilled water and to it added, solutions of ammonium carbonate (5 ml) and PBHA (1 ml) and mixed thoroughly. Then chloroform (10 ml) was added to the mixture and shaken for 3-4 min to extract aluminium-PBHA complex. The phases were allowed to separate and the organic layer alongwith chloroform washings (3 × 2 ml) transferred to a volumetric flask after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. To it was added morin solution (1 ml) and finally diluted to 25 ml with chloroform-alcohol mixture such as to maintain the solvents ratio 4 : 1 (v/v) in the final solution. The solution was warmed for 5 min on water bath at 55° for the colour development. The loss of volume due to warming was compensated by adding the solvent mixture.

The absorbance of the aluminium-PBHA-morin complex was measured at 430 nm against the reagent blank. The fluorescence intensity of aluminium-PBHA-morin complex solution was measured against the blank.

Results and Discussion

The aluminium-PBHA complex is colourless. The aluminium-PBHA-morin complex is greenish

yellow in colour having a maximum absorbance at 430 nm and gives the fluorescence.

Effect of pH and shaking time : The extractions were carried out at pH 7.0-9.0 and it was revealed that the maximum extraction is obtained at pH 8.0-8.8 (Table 1). 5 ml aliquot of ammonium carbonate solution gives the pH 8.8 which is most suitable for the extraction purpose. Complete extraction of aluminium-PBHA complex in chloroform was obtained by shaking for 3 min. The aqueous layer was tested for aluminium by alizarin-S¹ and indicated its absence.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON THE EXTRACTION OF ALUMINIUM

Aluminium : 2.0 ppm, Solvent : Chloroform : EtOH (4 : 1), PBHA (0.5 % EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Morin (0.1 % EtOH) : 1.0 ml, λ_{max} : 430 nm

pH	Absorbance	E %	Molar absorptivity l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
7.0	0.65	73	8.8 × 10 ⁴
7.6	0.73	82	9.8 × 10 ⁴
8.0	0.90	100	1.2 × 10 ⁵
8.4	0.90	100	1.2 × 10 ⁵
8.8	0.90	100	1.2 × 10 ⁵
9.0	0.33	37	4.5 × 10 ⁴

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MORIN CONCENTRATION ON THE EXTRACTION OF ALUMINIUM

Aluminium : 2.0 ppm, pH : 8.8, PBHA (0.5 % EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Solvent : Chloroform : EtOH (4 : 1), λ_{max} : 430 nm, Morin : 0.1% in EtOH

Morin soln. ml.	Absorbance	Molar absorptivity l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
0.5	0.57	7.7 × 10 ⁴
0.8	0.70	9.4 × 10 ⁴
1.0	0.89	1.2 × 10 ⁵
1.5	0.89	1.2 × 10 ⁵
1.8	*	*
2.0	*	*

* Turbid.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF THE SOLVENTS ON THE EXTRACTION OF ALUMINIUM

Aluminium : 2.0 ppm, pH : 8.8, PBHA (0.5% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Morin (0.1% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Solvent : Chloroform—EtOH (4 : 1)

Solvent	λ_{max} nm	Molar absorptivity l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Fluorimeter reading (div.)
Chloroform	430	1.2 × 10 ⁴	100
Benzene	436	1.0 × 10 ⁴	60
MIBK	419	4.3 × 10 ³	36
Isoamyl alcohol	*	*	*

* Complex not extractable.

Effect of reagent concentration : A study with varying concentration of PBHA at the optimum conditions reveals that a single extraction with 1 ml PBHA solution (0.5%) was enough for quantitative extraction. Lower reagent concentrations gave incomplete extractions. A study with varying concentrations of morin keeping PBHA concentration constant reveals that 1.0 ml morin solution (0.1%) gives the most satisfactory result (Table 2). The

TABLE 4—VALIDITY OF BEER'S LAW

Solvent : Chloroform : EtOH (4 : 1), Morin (0.1% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, PBHA (0.5% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, λ_{max} : 430 nm, pH : 8.8

Aluminium ppm	Absorbance	Fluorimeter readings
0.02	0.009	2.5
0.05	0.023	6.2
0.10	0.045	12.5
0.20	0.090	25.0
0.40	0.180	50.0
0.60	0.270	75.0
0.80	0.360	100.0
1.00	0.450	—
1.20	0.540	—
1.40	0.630	—
1.60	0.720	—
2.00	0.900	—
2.40	1.080	—
3.00	1.350	—

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON EXTRACTION OF ALUMINIUM

Aluminium : 2.0 ppm, pH : 8.8, PBHA (0.5% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Morin (0.1% EtOH) : 1.0 ml, Solvent : Chloroform : EtOH (4 : 1), λ_{max} : 430 nm, Absorbance : 0.90

Ions	Added as	Amount	Absorbance
Na ⁺	NaCl	50	0.90
K ⁺	KCl	50	0.90
Li ⁺	LiCl	50	0.90
Ca ⁺⁺	CaCl ₂	50	0.90
Sr ⁺⁺	SrSO ₄	50	0.90
Mg ⁺⁺	MgCl ₂	50	0.90
Cu ⁺⁺	CuSO ₄	50	0.91
Ni ⁺⁺	NiCl ₂	50	0.89
Pb ⁺⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	50	0.90
Fe ⁺⁺	FeCl ₃	60	0.89
Bi ⁺⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃	50	0.89
Th ⁺⁺	Th(NO ₃) ₄	50	0.89
Sb ⁺⁺	Sb ₂ Cl ₃	50	0.91
V ⁺⁺	VO ₂ Cl ₂	50	0.90
Ba ⁺⁺	BaCl ₂	100	0.91
Be ⁺⁺	BeCl ₂	100	0.89
Cd ⁺⁺	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	100	0.90
Mn ⁺⁺	MnSO ₄	100	0.90
Ce ⁺⁺	Ce(SO ₄) ₃	80	0.89
Sn ⁺⁺	SnCl ₄	80	0.89
Cl ⁻	KCl	50	0.90
Br ⁻	KBr	50	0.90
I ⁻	KI	50	0.90
NO ₃ ⁻	KNO ₃	50	0.90
SO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ SO ₄	50	0.89
BO ₃ ⁻	Na ₂ BO ₃	50	0.89
PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₃ PO ₄	50	0.89
CO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ CO ₃	50	0.90

higher morin concentration gives turbidity and the lower one reduces the colour intensity.

Effect of solvents and stability : Amongst the several solvents chloroform, benzene, methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) and isoamyl alcohol, chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent for extraction of aluminium (Table 3). The aluminium-PBHA-morin complex was found to show constant absorbance when a 4 : 1 ratio of chloroform ethanol mixture was taken. Further, the complete colour development takes 25 min but

on heating the complex to 55° this time is reduced to 5 min. The complexes were found to be stable for several days and absorbance was found to remain constant.

Beer's law: The aluminium as aluminium-PBHA-morin complex obeys the Beer's law within 0-3 ppm (Table 4) and the molar absorptivity was found to be $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 430 nm. In the fluorimetric determination the Beer's law limits were found to be 0-0.8 ppm.

Effect of diverse ions: Table 5 shows the effect of various diverse ions for the determination of aluminium. The experiments were made on aqueous solutions containing 2.0 ppm of aluminium in presence of various amounts of diverse ions. Moderate amount of many ions commonly associated with aluminium can be tolerated.

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